

Article type: Review

Strategies to overcome autofluorescence in nanoprobe-driven in vivo fluorescence imaging

Blanca del Rosal and Antonio Benayas**

Dr. B. del Rosal

Centre for Micro-Photonics, Faculty of Science, Engineering and Technology, Swinburne University of Technology, PO Box 218, Hawthorn, VIC 3122, Australia
E-mail: bdelrosalrabes@swin.edu.au

Dr. A. Benayas

Department of Physics and CICECO – Aveiro Institute of Materials, University of Aveiro, 3810-193, Aveiro, Portugal.
E-mail: abenayas@ua.pt

Department of Radiology, Stanford University, 1201 Welch Road, Lucas Center (exp.), Stanford, CA 94305-5484, United States of America

Keywords: Bioimaging, Autofluorescence, Infrared, Nanoparticles

The development of fluorescent probes and optical detection systems in the near infrared (700-2000 nm) has boosted the interest in fluorescence bioimaging as an alternative to traditional medical imaging techniques. Fluorescence imaging can provide high-resolution images at fast acquisition speeds, while removing the need for ionizing radiations or radioactive contrast agents and requiring relatively simple and cost-effective equipment. The low absorption and scattering of near infrared radiation by biological tissues enables minimally invasive visualization of deeply embedded organs and structures. However, the infrared autofluorescence background generated by some biological components, as discussed in this review, can negatively affect the image contrast and complicate the visualization of the fluorescent probes used as contrast agents. A critical review on the different approaches for improving the signal-to-noise ratio in in vivo fluorescence imaging experiments through autofluorescence background removal is presented here.

1. Introduction

Fluorescence imaging is a well-established research tool in the biomedical field, where major breakthroughs have been facilitated by the advances in fluorescence microscopy instrumentation and contrast agents.^[1] Most of these operate in the visible range of the electromagnetic spectrum, where the high absorption and scattering of light by tissues results in very low penetration depths.^[2] This limited the usefulness of fluorescence imaging in the clinical practice, where high quality imaging of deeply embedded anatomical structures is essential. This limitation has been largely overcome by the development of biocompatible fluorescent probes operating in the near infrared (NIR, 700-2000 nm), where high contrast imaging is possible at greater penetration depths owing to a marked reduction in light absorption and scattering.^[3] That spectral range is usually split in different regions known as biological windows, typically labeled as NIR-I (650-950nm), NIR-II (1000-1350nm) and NIR-III –or NIR IIb– (1550-1870nm).^[4]

NIR fluorescence imaging has attracted a great deal of attention in the past decade, which has translated into advances in NIR imaging instrumentation and multiple novel NIR contrast agents.^[5] The interest in NIR in vivo fluorescence imaging has been boosted by the development of NIR nanomaterials that can offer not only fluorescence contrast but also additional functionalities, including multimodal imaging, targeting to specific tissues and therapeutic capabilities.^[4, 6] Several nanoparticle-based NIR contrast agents have been used in biomedical research, although some limitations still need to be overcome before considering their clinical application, as is reviewed in detail in the work published by Hong et al. in 2017.^[7] In terms of relevance and feasibility to render useful fluorescence in vivo imaging both in basic research and at the preclinical level (and potentially, at the clinical level in the foreseeable future), research efforts are now focused on imaging in the NIR spectral range. Therefore, in this paper we will strictly focus on NIR fluorescence imaging.

NIR fluorescence imaging presents several key features that make it particularly interesting for biomedical research and for the clinical practice. As opposed to the commonly used clinical imaging modalities, fluorescence imaging is capable of real time image acquisition, enabling dynamic visualization of physiological and metabolic processes with a high spatial resolution.^[8] That imaging speed is widely recognized as the major advantage of fluorescence imaging compared with other imaging modalities, -magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), positron emission tomography (PET), computerized tomography by X-rays (CT)-, most of which place ahead in terms of effective clinical implementation. Moreover, not requiring ionizing radiation or radioactive contrast agents, it raises little safety concerns even for repeated imaging procedures. The adoption of fluorescence imaging as a clinical imaging tool could also help in reducing the economic burden on healthcare systems thanks to the relatively low cost of the required instrumentation and the versatility of the imaging setups.^{[1a,}

9]

The sensitivity of any imaging technique depends on the achieved signal-to-noise ratio. In the case of fluorescence imaging, this can be impaired by tissue autofluorescence, which in the worst-case scenario can completely mask the fluorescence emission of the probes used as contrast agents. Most fluorophores responsible for autofluorescence, as will be discussed in Section 2, show their emission maxima in the visible, so that NIR autofluorescence was traditionally considered negligible.^[10] The development of more sensitive NIR detectors showed, however, that autofluorescence constitutes a remarkable problem for bioimaging even in this spectral range. Addressing the issue of autofluorescence is key for optimizing the sensitivity of NIR fluorescence imaging and help it become a widespread technique in clinical research and practice. As we present in Section 3, several imaging strategies with their correspondent experimental methodologies to minimize the contribution of autofluorescence to NIR fluorescence imaging have been proposed and evaluated in vivo.

Finally, in Section 4 we draw a comprehensive critical comparison of the different techniques, together with a prospective of the foreseeable progress in the next years following the current trends of research.

The scope of this review is restricted to the issue of addressing autofluorescence background affecting in vivo fluorescence imaging when nanoparticles are used as contrast agents. Hence, this allows to focus the topic of this review in the experimental methods used for autofluorescence removal without constituting a comprehensive account of all other materials currently used for NIR imaging (dyes, small organic molecules, semiconductor polymers and so on).^[7]

2. Autofluorescence in the infrared

Due to the presence of a variety of intrinsic fluorophores, biological tissues typically generate a fluorescence signal upon optical excitation. The origin of this phenomenon, known as autofluorescence, has been widely studied in the visible and ultraviolet ranges of the electromagnetic spectrum, where several biomolecules present excitation and emission bands.^[11] Pyridine nucleotids and flavines, aromatic aminoacids and structural proteins, as well as some lipopigments (lipofuscin and ceroids), have been identified as the main contributors to autofluorescence. Each of this intrinsic fluorophores presents specific spectroscopic features, which have been reviewed in detail by Richards-Kortum et al.^[12]

The content and distribution of intrinsic fluorophores in tissues change with physiological and pathological processes, which can therefore be characterized by analyzing the autofluorescence signal. For instance, the metabolic state of tissues can be analyzed by monitoring the autofluorescence associated to pyridine nucleotids and flavins, which are key players in cell energy metabolism and present distinct quantum yields depending on their oxidation state. This has been used not only to obtain three dimensional maps of the metabolic state of tissues,^[13] but also to successfully distinguish neoplastic cells from healthy

ones thanks to their differences in energy metabolism pathways.^[14] Autofluorescence has also proven useful for detection of atherosclerotic plaques in arterial tissue. Under excitation with visible light (458 and 476 nm), the emission spectrum of plaques is dominated by lipoprotein fluorescence, whereas elastin and collagen are the major contributors to autofluorescence in healthy arterial tissues.^[15]

These results indicate that autofluorescence can be used to differentiate between healthy and pathological tissue. This has led to the application of autofluorescence imaging in a variety of areas at the clinical level, ranging from the diagnosis of malignant tumors and cardiovascular pathologies to the study of bacterial population in teeth as a means to determine the presence of dental caries.^[16] Despite the usefulness of autofluorescence as a diagnostic tool, it becomes a major limitation for obtaining high contrast images when using fluorescent markers to label specific structures or visualize processes occurring in living organisms. The presence of an autofluorescence background hinders the signal to noise ratio of fluorescence images and can, in the worst-case scenario, completely mask the emission of the contrast agents that need to be visualized.

Whereas autofluorescence in the visible and ultraviolet ranges of the spectrum has been extensively studied and characterized, NIR autofluorescence upon NIR excitation remained mostly unexplored and had been considered virtually negligible until the past few years.^[10] However, the advantages of NIR for bioimaging in living organisms in terms of optimized penetration depth and minimal scattering have brought about the development of new NIR-operating fluorescent contrast agents. This, together with the availability of more sensitive imaging cameras in this spectral range has boosted the research on NIR in vivo imaging, as discussed in Section 1. In this context, a variety of studies reported on significant autofluorescence backgrounds during NIR imaging experiments in small animal models. These studies indicated that, while the autofluorescence issue could be partially addressed by

choosing the NIR spectral range instead of the visible for imaging, additional strategies needed to be developed to further reduce its contribution and optimize the signal-to-noise ratio of in vivo NIR images.

Not many studies have been carried out in terms of identifying the specific biological components responsible for autofluorescence in the NIR. However, the currently available experimental evidence allows us to pinpoint two major contributors to the background observed in NIR in vivo images: chlorophyll and melanin.

Even though chlorophyll might seem to have little relevance in the case of small animal imaging, that in fact is not the case, as chlorophyll-containing alfalfa is one of the major components of laboratory rodent diet. Several authors have reported on a strong autofluorescence signal, both at the skin surface and in the digestive tract of mice that could be unequivocally attributed to the presence of chlorophyll in their diet.^[17]

Chlorophyll fluorescence has been characterized in depth and has become a widespread tool in plant physiology for assessing photosynthesis activity.^[18] Green plants present two chemically distinct varieties of this pigment, chlorophyll *a* and chlorophyll *b*, which present slightly different spectroscopic properties. Both of them present excitation bands in the blue and far-red ranges of the electromagnetic spectrum and emission bands beyond 650 nm.^[19] However, an energy transfer process from chlorophyll *b* to chlorophyll *a* results in the latter being the main contributor to chlorophyll fluorescence emission.^[19-20] Chlorophyll *a* presents two excitation maxima at 485 and 665 nm, respectively, and an emission band at 682 nm with a shoulder peak at around 740 nm which extends into the infrared.^[19, 21]

Weagle et al. were the first to relate in vivo NIR autofluorescence to chlorophyll, after having observed a non-negligible fluorescence background when studying the biosynthesis and clearance of protoporphyrin IX in nude mice.^[22] The authors recorded the in vivo emission spectra (in the 300-800 nm range) of the mice upon excitation at 405 nm, observing an

emission band centered at 674 nm in addition to the two protoporphyrin IX peaks (centered at 635 and 700 nm). This band was particularly intense in the abdominal area, which led the authors to analyze the ex vivo fluorescence of the abdominal organs finding the emission signal was highest in the stomach. Moreover, the excitation and emission spectra obtained for undigested contents of the mice stomachs and food pellets (both dry and extracted in ethanol) were very similar to those recorded for mice skin. An ethanol extraction of alfalfa leaves presented very similar spectral features, confirming the key role played by this food component in the autofluorescence signal. The authors attributed the observed autofluorescence to pheophytin *a* and pheophorbide *a*, derivatives of chlorophyll *a*, which present very similar spectral features including emission bands centered at around 675 and 720 nm. König et al. corroborated the relation between the strong autofluorescence signal observed in nude mice, particularly in the abdominal area, and the composition of their diet.^[23] They analyzed the fluorescence of the raw components of food pellets and found in vivo autofluorescence correlated with the chlorophyll-containing cereal products. These presented intense emission bands in the far-red and NIR ranges of the electromagnetic spectrum. This led to the development of fluorescence-free rodent diet, which was first proposed by Weagle's group in 1995,^[24] and then became common practice as alfalfa-free and purified rodent diets were made commercially available products.^[17b-e] Troy et al. carried out an in-depth study in 2004 where in vivo fluorescence imaging was used to quantify autofluorescence in nude mice fed either a conventional or an alfalfa-free diet. The latter produced a significant reduction in the digestive tract autofluorescence in the NIR spectral range (705-780 nm excitation and 810-885 nm emission), but did not result in a complete elimination of the autofluorescence signal. The remaining NIR background signal was attributed to some metabolic processes, excluding chlorophyll as the sole cause of NIR in vivo autofluorescence. The relation between diet and abdominal autofluorescence was further

explored by Inoue et al., who measured food pellet autofluorescence for regular, alfalfa-free and purified (composed of milk casein, cornstarch, sugar, corn oil, vitamins and minerals) rodent diets in different spectral ranges.^[17c] Whereas purified diet presented the lowest fluorescence in the NIR range (672.5-747.5 nm excitation and 775-825 nm emission), its emission signal could still be detected by the commercial IVIS imaging system used in this report. Food-related autofluorescence constitutes an issue at longer excitation and emission wavelengths too, as reported by Villa et al in 2015.^[17a] They observed a significant background in fluorescence images recorded using an InGaAs camera in the 900-1700 nm range upon excitation with 808 nm laser light. **Figure 1a** shows the NIR fluorescence images of a regular rodent food pellet as obtained under 808 nm excitation, indicating food-associated autofluorescence is an issue that needs to be considered in NIR imaging, not only in the first biological window, but also in the second. This was confirmed in 2016 by del Rosal et al., who measured the emission spectra of regular rodent diet under 808 nm excitation, finding an emission band which extended beyond 1200 nm as is shown in **Figure 1b**.^[25] To the best of our knowledge, to this date no study has been performed to evaluate the effect of alfalfa-free or purified diets in in vivo autofluorescence for these excitation and emission wavelengths.

Figure 1. Food-related autofluorescence. a) NIR fluorescence images obtained under 808 nm laser excitation for a regular (chlorophyll-containing) rodent food pellet. Adapted with permission.^[88] b) NIR emission spectrum obtained for the food pellet shown in a. Adapted with permission.^[25] Copyright 2016, Wiley-VCH.

As we indicated previously, melanin is another major contributor to the overall background in the NIR. The color of skin and hair in animals is determined by the quantity and distribution of these chromophores, which can be classified in two major groups (eumelanins and pheomelanins) with distinct chemical structures and properties.^[26] Skin autofluorescence had been widely explored in the 1990s in the UV and visible ranges of the spectrum.^[27] At these wavelengths, autofluorescence is mainly attributed to aminoacids and structural protein, whereas melanin fluorescence is extremely weak, even leading to it being considered a non-fluorescent chromophore by some authors.^[28] However, this is no longer the case when wavelengths in the NIR are considered. Huang et al first reported the relation between melanin and NIR autofluorescence of the skin in 2006, when they studied melanin emission both in vitro and in vivo upon excitation with 785 nm laser light. Their in vitro experiments indicated that solid state melanins (both synthetic and natural) showed an intense emission signal spanning their detection range (840-920 nm). This NIR emission, shown in **Figure 2a**, followed an increasing trend for longer wavelengths and two bands, at 880 and 890 nm, that corresponded to Raman scattering by melanin.^[29] Skin appendages (human hair, feline fur and feathers) with black pigmentation showed very similar autofluorescence spectra, whereas their white counterparts showed a much less intense emission and a decreasing trend with increasing wavelengths, which could be explained taking into account the different melanin content.^[30]

Melanin autofluorescence, despite being an undesirable source of background noise for NIR bioimaging, has demonstrated potential as a diagnostic tool for pigmented skin lesions, including melanoma.^[31] Melanin has also been found to be the major contributor to eye

fundus NIR autofluorescence, as was first suggested by Piccolino et al. in 1996, who observed a NIR background in several pathological ocular structures upon excitation with 805 nm laser light during ICG angiography.^[32] Up to that moment, ocular autofluorescence had only been studied and explored as a diagnosis tool in the visible range of the spectrum, where it is caused not by melanin but by lipofuscins.^[33] Keilhauer and Delori performed an in-depth study of ocular NIR autofluorescence using 787 nm as excitation wavelength and found that it originated from the melanin in both the retinal pigment epithelium and choroid.^[34] NIR autofluorescence imaging can also be applied for diagnosis of retinal pathologies, being more comfortable for the patient than the more widespread visible fundus autofluorescence imaging, as well as not presenting the potential to advance the progression of retinal diseases.^[35]

The great majority of the studies on NIR melanin autofluorescence have been restricted to the first biological window, and its spectral properties have not been characterized for wavelengths beyond 1000 nm. The only existing study thus far addressing the association between melanin and autofluorescence in the second biological window was carried out by del Rosal et al. in 2016.^[36] The authors systematically studied the in vivo and ex vivo autofluorescence of mice pertaining to five different lab mice strains with distinct coat colors. They found that, upon optical excitation at 808 nm, highly pigmented individuals presented a higher skin autofluorescence intensity throughout the whole detection range (900-1700 nm). This can be easily appreciated in in **Figure 2b**, where the in vivo infrared images obtained by the authors for each of the mice strains studies are represented for two different detection ranges: 900-1700 nm and 1200-1700 nm.

Figure 2b indicates melanin autofluorescence intensity is reduced for longer wavelengths. This is the same trend followed by the ex vivo NIR autofluorescence observed upon 808 nm excitation for several mouse organs, particularly the liver, spleen and kidneys.^[36-37] All these

organs show an intense autofluorescence in the 900-1700 nm detection range, whereas this signal is virtually negligible beyond 1200 nm, as can be seen in detail in **Figure 2c**. NIR autofluorescence in these organs has been attributed to the accumulation of a variety of endogenous fluorophores, including flavins, lipofuscins and reticulon fibers. All these pigments are markedly fluorescent in the visible,^[38] although no characterization of their NIR autofluorescence upon NIR excitation has been carried out so far.

Figure 2. Pigmentation-related autofluorescence. a) NIR autofluorescence spectrum obtained from natural melanin isolated from *Sepia officinalis* (Sigma, M2649) upon excitation at 785 nm. Adapted with permission.^[29] Copyright 2004, SPIE. b) NIR in vivo autofluorescence images of mice strains with different coat colors in two spectral ranges (900-1700 nm and 1200-1700 nm) obtained upon excitation at 808 nm ($0.2 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$). Reproduced with permission.^[36] Copyright 2015, Wiley-VCH. c) NIR ex vivo autofluorescence images of representative mouse liver, spleen and kidneys obtained under the same conditions as the images in b. Adapted with permission.^[88]

The intensity of chlorophyll-related autofluorescence beyond 900 nm also decreased for increasing wavelengths (see Figure 1), so that we can generally state that in vivo NIR autofluorescence background can be minimized by imaging at longer wavelengths. Melanin and chlorophyll share another common spectroscopic feature, which is characteristic of most

organic compounds: they present relatively short (\sim ns) fluorescence lifetimes.^[18d, 39] As will be explained in detail in the following section, autofluorescence removal during in vivo imaging has been tackled by different research groups by taking advantage of either of these common characteristics of the chromophores responsible for this undesirable background noise.

3. Techniques for overcoming autofluorescence

Experimental approaches devised by researchers to perform autofluorescence-free in vivo fluorescence imaging can be classified in two main groups: lifetime-based methods and wavelength-based methods. Each method requires combining an adequate experimental setup with fluorescent contrast agents that satisfy a specific set of requirements, as will be explained in detail in the following subsections.

While the self-evident ultimate goal of suppressing autofluorescence is to maximize the value of the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), the methods summarized in this work focus on minimizing the quantitative value of the denominator in that ratio (that is, reducing the noise). The complementary approach for increasing SNR by maximizing the numerator (i.e. increasing the signal intensity) is an ongoing quest for researchers in the field of fluorescence in vivo imaging. That strategy for increasing the brightness of the probes through optimization of both their absorbance and fluorescence quantum yield falls beyond the scope of this work.

3.1. Wavelength-based methods

The first group of techniques calls for fluorescent probes whose excitation and/or emission bands overlap as little as possible with those of intrinsic autofluorophores. We can further classify these methods in two groups depending on whether they are based on selecting a specific excitation wavelength or on spectrally filtering the fluorescence emission. It is noteworthy that the former approach seeks to avoid or minimize generating autofluorescence,

while the latter focus on screening the fluorescence detector from the autofluorescence generated, as an undesired side-product, by the optical stimulation.

3.1.1. Excitation wavelength selection

Several authors have evaluated the effect of the excitation wavelength on the autofluorescence intensity in the visible and NIR. In the previous section, we commented on the work presented by Troy et al. in 2004, in which diet-related in vivo autofluorescence was studied.^[17e] The authors used a commercially available preclinical system (IVIS Imaging System) capable of small animal imaging in the 400-950 nm wavelength range. Using a broadband (400-1000 nm) halogen lamp for optical excitation and adequate sets of filters to select the desired excitation and emission wavelengths enabled the authors to study the wavelength dependence of in vivo autofluorescence. Their results showed that NIR excitation (705-780 nm) and emission (810-885 nm) produced the lowest autofluorescence background, although it was still higher than the instrument noise level. Bhaumik et al. reached similar conclusions using a different commercial system (eXplore Optix, which will be described in detail in section 3.2) and studying the autofluorescence intensity at four different excitation wavelengths (440, 635, 670, and 785 nm).^[17f] The authors noted that 785 nm excitation generated the lowest autofluorescence background. However, the results obtained in both these studies indicate that excitation wavelength selection alone is not enough to obtain autofluorescence-free images.

The lack of adequate fluorescence contrast agents prevented further exploration of this technique at longer excitation wavelengths until the development of biocompatible upconverting nanoparticles (UCNPs). Upconversion is the general term used to describe the emission of higher energy photons from lower energy excitation through multiphoton processes. These multiphoton mechanisms, as well as the synthesis procedures and biomedical applicability of UCNPs have already been extensively reviewed.^[40] Both Zhou et

al., in 2012, and Wu et al., in 2015, presented detailed reviews of the application of upconversion luminescence in small animal imaging.^[41] UCNPs of interest for autofluorescence-free bioimaging are typically co-doped with Yb^{3+} ions, which can be optically excited at around 980 nm, and a different rare earth ion (typically Er^{3+} or Tm^{3+}) that can generate luminescence at a shorter wavelength. $\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Tm}^{3+}$ co-doped UCNPs present the advantage of an enhanced penetration depth with respect to $\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Er}^{3+}$ systems, as thulium ions display an emission band at 800 nm, within the first biological window (650-980 nm), whereas the emission of Er^{3+} ions is limited to visible wavelengths.

In 2008, Prasad's group demonstrated *in vivo* bioimaging with UCNPs as contrast agents for the first time using $\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Tm}^{3+}$ co-doped NaYF_4 NPs.^[42] Using a 975 nm diode laser for excitation and a commercial IVIS Maestro system for detection, the authors were capable of detecting the upconversion emission after intravenous injection of a NP-containing dispersion. However, as shown in **Figure 3a**, a non-negligible autofluorescence background was present in the obtained images. In the following years, numerous demonstrations of the applicability of $\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Tm}^{3+}$ and $\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Er}^{3+}$ co-doped NPs for *in vivo* bioimaging were carried out by different groups.^[43] In all cases, an imaging system very similar to that used by Xiong et al. in 2009 (schematically shown in **Figure 3b**) was employed.^[44] Generally, these imaging setups rely on a CCD camera to record the *in vivo* fluorescence images obtained under optical excitation with a 980 nm CW laser diode. A bandpass filter placed in the detection path is used to further improve the image contrast.

Figure 3. Excitation wavelength selection. a) In vivo and ex vivo spectrally unmixed images of a mouse intravenously injected with UCNPs obtained with a Maestro imaging system upon excitation at 985 nm. The red and green areas correspond to the NP signal and the autofluorescence background, respectively. The inset shows the 700-850 nm emission spectra corresponding to the UCNPs (red curve) and the autofluorescence background (green curve) as well as the background noise (black curve). Adapted with permission.^[42] Copyright 2008, American Chemical Society. b) Diagram representing a typical experimental setup for in vivo imaging with upconversion nanoparticles. Optical excitation is provided by a 980 nm laser and optical filters are placed in the detection path to avoid any contribution from scattered excitation light. Reproduced with permission.^[44] Copyright 2009, American Chemical Society. c) In vivo whole body optical and fluorescence images of a nude mouse subcutaneously injected with UCNPs (emission maxima at 800 nm). The fluorescence image was obtained with a Maestro imaging system under 915 nm excitation. Adapted with permission.^[47] Copyright 2011, American Chemical Society.

Relying on excitation at 980 nm, as required by most UCNPs, constitutes an important limitation for bioimaging applications, as this wavelength is partially absorbed by water.^[45] This not only results in the attenuation of the excitation light as it penetrates into biological tissues, but also causes non-specific laser-induced heating during the imaging process that can lead to irreversible damage.^[46] In 2011, Zhan et al. demonstrated optical excitation at 915 nm was adequate for reducing the laser induced heating during in vivo imaging with co-doped $\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Tm}^{3+}$ NaYbF_4 NPs.^[47] Their imaging experiments, performed in nude mice using a Maestro imaging system, showed a minimum autofluorescence background upon 915 nm excitation as shown in **Figure 3c**.

A proven strategy for synthesizing UCNPs that can be optically excited at other wavelengths within the first biological window involves including different rare earth ions as dopants. For instance, NPs doped with Nd³⁺ ions can be optically excited at around 800 nm, which constitutes a far better option for bioimaging as light-induced heating is minimized. Several approaches for synthesizing triply doped (Nd³⁺/Yb³⁺/Er³⁺ or Tm³⁺) UCNPs that can be excited at this wavelength have been proposed.^[48] Wang et al. demonstrated that an adequate distribution of the doping ions in the NP structure could result in efficient optical excitation at 800 nm. The penetration depth of this excitation wavelength in a phantom tissue was very similar to that at 980 nm, while producing minimal in vivo laser-induced heating.^[48a]

To summarize, relying on excitation wavelengths within the first biological window using UCNPs as in vivo contrast agents is a useful tool for reducing the autofluorescence background during in vivo NIR imaging. The low absorption of autofluorophores in that spectral range combined with the use of bandpass filters in the detection path to select the upconversion emission enables for virtually autofluorescence-free in vivo imaging. However, this has not been confirmed by any studies on pigmented animals or UCNPs biodistribution studies, where a possible interference of upconversion emission and food- and pigmentation-related autofluorescence could have been observed.

3.1.2. Emission wavelength selection

As described in Section 2 (see figures 1 and 2), in vivo food- and pigmentation-associated NIR autofluorescence intensity decreases for wavelengths in the second biological window (NIR-II). Several groups have reported in the past five years on the successful application of fluorescent probes emitting in this spectral range for autofluorescence-free bioimaging.^[7] Moreover, fluorescence imaging in NIR-II offers a substantial advantage from the spatial resolution standpoint as light scattering by tissues decreases with increasing wavelength as λ^{-x} , where x represents a tissue-dependent constant.^[2c, 49]

In vivo imaging had not been explored beyond the first biological window until a few years ago due to the lack of contrast agents and the unsuitability of the silicon detectors typically used for small animal imaging. The spectral sensitivity of silicon detectors drops abruptly at around 1000 nm, so that less affordable InGaAs cameras (sensitive in the 900-1700 nm range) are required for imaging at longer wavelengths.^[3b] A light source for optical excitation in the first biological window (typically, an 808 nm laser) and long pass filters placed in the detection path, together with an InGaAs detector, constitute the typical setup for autofluorescence-free imaging based on spectral filtering of the emission signal. The optical filters are key for obtaining autofluorescence-free images, as well as for eliminating any contribution of the scattered excitation light.

The first demonstration of in vivo imaging in the second biological window was carried out by Hongjie Dai's group in 2009.^[50] By collecting whole-body fluorescence images in the 1100-1700 nm range of nude mice intravenously injected with SWNTs, they achieved visualization of their vasculature with minimal autofluorescence background, as shown in **Figure 4a**. The authors also monitored tumor vasculature through high (50x) magnification images, demonstrating the capability of this approach for resolving very small blood vessels (up to a few micrometers) below the skin. Subsequent works have confirmed the superiority of NIR-II for fluorescence bioimaging with a high spatial resolution, either using SWNTs as contrast agents^[37, 51] or reporting on novel biocompatible fluorescent nanoprobe operating in this spectral range. These include Ag₂S quantum dots,^[52] organic and polymeric nanoparticles,^[8b, 53] PbS-based quantum dots^[54] and lanthanide-doped systems.^[17a, 55] Two of these studies deal specifically with how spectrally filtering the emission signal before image collection can result in autofluorescence removal. In 2014, Villa et al. reported on NIR bioimaging using neodymium-doped SrF₂ NPs and found that food- and pigment- associated autofluorescence did not allow for adequately characterizing NP biodistribution in vivo or ex

vivo when imaging in the 900-1700 nm range.^[17a] Autofluorescence-free imaging with these NPs was possible by filtering out the emission signals shorter than 1300 nm. In the 1300-1700 nm range, the NPs could be unequivocally detected by fluorescence imaging thanks to Nd³⁺ ions displaying an emission band at around 1340 nm. A year later, a study carried out by Dai's group evaluated in vivo and ex vivo autofluorescence throughout the second biological window and analyzed its impact on biodistribution experiments of intravenously injected SWNTs.^[37] Spectrally filtering the emission signal allowed them to quantify the autofluorescence intensity, upon 808 nm optical excitation, within different spectral ranges. Their results, as displayed in **Figure 4b**, indicate that autofluorescence-free bioimaging could only be achieved in the 1500-1700 nm spectral range, corresponding to NIR-IIb. When compared to imaging in the whole 1000-1700 nm range, restricting the emission range to NIR-IIb resulted in an 80-fold reduction in the in vivo autofluorescence at the liver. This constitutes a 4-fold improvement with respect to the autofluorescence intensity measured for wavelengths above 1300 nm. As shown in **Figure 4c**, ex vivo SWNT detection in the liver, which presents a high intrinsic fluorescence,^[36] was only possible when filtering the emission to the NIR-IIb spectral range, as autofluorescence completely masked their emission at shorter wavelengths.

Figure 4. Emission wavelength selection. a) In vivo images of a nude mouse intravenously injected with carbon nanotubes (left) and an untreated nude mouse (right). The excitation wavelength was 808 nm, while the detection range was limited to 1100-1700 nm. Adapted with permission.^[50] Copyright 2009, Nature Publishing Group. b) In vivo autofluorescence images of a mouse (abdomen skin open) in three different spectral ranges obtained under excitation with an 808 nm laser. Adapted with permission.^[37] Copyright 2015, Springer. c) Fluorescence images in three spectral ranges of a liver tissue slice pertaining to a mouse intravenously injected with carbon nanotubes. An 808 nm laser was used for optical excitation. Adapted with permission.^[37] Copyright 2015, Springer.

3.2. Lifetime methods

These techniques rely on contrast agents presenting longer fluorescence lifetimes (ideally, at least by two orders of magnitude) than those characteristic of autofluorophores, which, as indicated in Section 2, are in the order of a few nanoseconds. The fluorescence generated by these probes can be detected even when image collection starts a certain time after the excitation light has been switched off. This, in turn, enables successfully filtering out the short-lived autofluorescence signal from the recorded images. A great variety of nanomaterials with excitation and emission bands in the biological windows and long fluorescence decay times have been developed and led to the development of two distinct strategies for lifetime-based autofluorescence-free imaging: time-gating and persistent luminescence. The main difference between these techniques, which will be described in full

detail in the following paragraphs, is how and when the fluorophores are optically excited. Time-gated imaging (TGI) is typically used with probes whose fluorescence lifetimes lie in the micro- to millisecond range, and thus require integration of the excitation source in the imaging setup. In the case of persistent luminescence, contrast agents present much longer decay times (typically, in the minutes to hours timescale), allowing excitation to be exclusively performed before starting the imaging experiments.

Aside from the techniques described below, in very specific cases is possible to take advantage

3.2.1. Time gated imaging

TGI was first proposed (in the 1970s) as a tool that could the sensitivity of fluorescence microscopy immunoassays by decreasing the intensity of the background.^[56] The basis of TGI lies on the combination of a pulsed excitation source and a delay system, so that image acquisition does not start until a certain delay time after the end of the excitation pulse has elapsed. When image collection starts, autofluorescence will no longer be detectable by the camera so that only the emission of the fluorophores employed as contrast agents will be registered.

Since the development of the first experimental setup capable of time-gated microscopy, presented by Soini et al. in 1998,^[57] a great variety of systems have been developed for this purpose. In general, time-gated gated-microscopy relies on a pulsed visible or UV source for optical excitation, with traditionally used flash lamps being replaced by pulsed LEDs in the more recent systems. Earlier systems achieved delayed detection by synchronizing a mechanical chopper to the excitation source to block the emission from reaching the CCD camera used for image collection, with later approaches relying on intensified-gated or electron-multiplying CCD cameras. Details of the evolution of time-gated microscopy systems, with a special focus on the instrumentation, can be found in the review authored by

Connally and Piper in 2008.^[58] Time-gated microscopy has found application in the biomedical research field for imaging cellular processes and structures.^[59]

Application of TGI to small animal imaging calls for long-lifetime fluorophores operating in the biological windows in order to ensure a maximum penetration of the excitation and emission light into tissues. Different approaches for in vivo TGI with varying degrees of complexity and flexibility in terms of excitation sources and range of delay times have been proposed in the past few years.

In vivo TGI was first demonstrated by Cubeddu et al. in 1992, who developed an experimental setup that relied on a nitrogen-pumped pulsed dye laser operating at 405 nm for excitation and an intensified CCD camera for detection.^[60] A programmable pulse generator was used to determine the width of the acquisition window and the delay time, which could be adjusted in the 0-30 ns range. The authors tested the in vivo performance of the system in tumor diagnosis in a murine model using a hematoporphyrin derivative, which presents an average fluorescence lifetime of 14 ns, as a tumor-selective fluorescent label. Optimum image contrast was achieved in this case when the delay time was set to 15 ns, however, this did not allow for a complete removal of the autofluorescence background. In an effort to further minimize the autofluorescence, the authors tested different excitation wavelengths (610, 650 and 670 nm) in a later work.^[61] In this case, the short lifetime of the compound used as fluorescent tumor marker (sulphonated aluminium phthalocyanine, which presents an average lifetime of 6 ns) required shorter delay times, no longer than 3 ns, for TGI. Therefore, even though the authors achieved a reduction in the intensity of the autofluorescence background by using red excitation rather than UV (337 nm) excitation, autofluorescence-free imaging was not realized.

The next reports on TGI for autofluorescence removal were carried out using a commercial system developed for in vivo imaging in the time domain. The design of this system, based

on the analysis of the temporal point spread function over a selected region of interest, was reported in 2004 by Gallant et al.^[62] This setup allowed both fluorescence intensity and lifetime mapping, fluorophore quantification and discrimination between fluorescence sources with overlapping emission bands but different lifetimes. It was commercially launched under the eXplore Optix name in 2004 by ART Advanced Research Technologies-GE Healthcare (Canada), becoming the first system for small animal imaging in the time domain to reach the market.^[63] For mapping the temporal point spread function, eXplore Optix relied on raster scanning of a pulsed laser over a user-defined region of interest (up to 20x9 cm) with a step size that could be adjusted between 0.5 and 3 mm. The pulsed diode laser of the initial version of this system operated at 670 nm and generated 100 ps pulses at an 80 MHz repetition rate with an average power tunable up to 500 μ W.^[62, 64] The excitation wavelength range was extended in subsequent updates; and the latest version of the system (Optix MX3, released in 2009) was equipped with a tunable laser in the 480-785 nm spectral range.^[64-65] A photomultiplier coupled to a time-correlated single photon counter was used for detection in the 400-900 nm range. This system is therefore not applicable for imaging fluorescent probes operating beyond the first biological window.

Although the Optix systems were not specifically designed for autofluorescence-free imaging, this can be achieved through adequate processing of the recorded fluorescence lifetime maps. This was first accomplished in 2012 by Hall et al., although their lifetime-based method was based on signal unmixing and cannot be strictly considered TGI. These authors reported on a strategy for autofluorescence removal during *in vivo* brain mapping of superoxide, an oxygen radical species that plays a relevant role in the function of the central nervous system.^[66] The authors labeled superoxide with a fluorescent compound (dihydroethidium, DHE), administered to mice via intraperitoneal injection, to enable *in vivo* superoxide detection by fluorescence imaging. Autofluorescence removal was achieved using

a MATLAB routine developed by the authors for fluorescence lifetime unmixing, based on their previous work for decoupling the emission signals corresponding to fluorophores with different lifetimes.^[67] This algorithm allowed decoupling the signal corresponding to DHE-labeled superoxide from tissue autofluorescence, resulting in an enhanced sensitivity and specificity and thus leading to the unequivocal in vivo identification of superoxide in different areas of the brain.

In 2013, Gu et al. implemented a TGI procedure for autofluorescence removal with this commercial system and studied its applicability by using long-lifetime (12 μ s) luminescent porous silicon NPs for tumor labelling in mice.^[68] In this case, the authors developed a MATLAB code to extract and temporally integrate the fluorescence intensity in the desired time window. Time-gated images were generated by integrating the recorded emission in the 18-19 ns time window after the end of the laser pulse. Pseudo-continuous wave (CW) images were obtained using the same MATLAB code, in this case by reconstructing the emission recorded in the full 25 ns imaging time window (corresponding to the laser pulse period). **Figure 5a** shows the pseudo continuous-wave (CW) and time-gated (TG) images as obtained for a tumor-bearing mouse before and after being inoculated with NPs in one of the tumors. This approach was also used by Ma in 2013 for obtaining background-free images of mice subcutaneously injected with quantum dots.^[65]

These results demonstrate that this method constitutes a valid approach for eliminating the autofluorescence background after image acquisition. However, being based on the manipulation of the lifetime data generated by the Optix system, it does not allow for autofluorescence-free imaging in real time, thus eliminating the possibility of live tracking fluorescence markers. This is further hindered by the fact that two dimensional scanning is an essential part of the imaging process, as we mentioned before, which results in very long acquisition times (in the order of several minutes) when compared to planar imaging

approaches.^[64] As an example, Hall et al. reported on an acquisition time of about 7 minutes for a 0.8 cm² area, although imaging time will vary depending on the requirements of each particular experiments in terms of exposure time, area and step size. These limitations make any system calling for two dimensional scanning extremely impractical for autofluorescence background removal during in vivo imaging experiments.

A system specifically devised for wide-field preclinical TGI was presented by May and coworkers in 2009.^[69] Two amplified phase-locked function generators were used to drive the pulsed LED array (operating at 630 nm and a repetition rate of 2 MHz) used as excitation source, as well as the gated intensified CCD camera that recorded the emission signal. The delay time was optimized to ~50 ns by monitoring the TGI contrast in real time for nude mice subcutaneously injected with QDs emitting at 705 nm with a lifetime of about 20 ns.

In vivo time-gated images were then compared to those obtained under pseudo-continuous wave conditions, where the image acquisition was not delayed with respect to the excitation pulse. The authors reported that the time-gated approach, despite requiring much longer acquisition times (up to 5 s, whereas only 0.125 ns were required under CW conditions) resulted in a three- to tenfold increase in the signal-to-noise ratio. This, in turn, improved the sensitivity, so that TGI enabled detection of lower QD concentrations (0.25 nM vs 2.5 nM), as is shown in **Figure 5b**. These results indicate that, while this TGI system achieved a significant reduction of the autofluorescence background, it did not allow for full autofluorescence removal.

Lanthanide-doped NPs, thanks to their long-lived fluorescence (micro- to millisecond),^[70] can be used for TGI with longer delay times between excitation and image collection than QDs. This had already been proposed and applied for autofluorescence-free luminescence microscopy, as reviewed by Connally and Piper in 2008.^[58] In the early 2010s, different strategies for simplifying the available systems for time-gated microscopy, which relied

mostly on gated intensified CCD cameras, were proposed and tested with lanthanide-based fluorescent probes.^[71] In 2011, Jin and Piper designed a low-cost approach for implementing TGI in a fluorescence microscope, based on synchronizing a pulsed excitation source with a mechanical chopper, whose geometry and speed determined the acquisition window.^[71c] With respect to CW conditions, this TGI approach resulted in an 18-fold improvement in the signal-to-noise ratio, as measured by the authors on *Giardia lamblia* cysts labeled with an europium-based complex.

Figure 5. Time-gated imaging. a) Comparison between continuous-wave and time-gated imaging in a tumor-bearing nude mouse before and after injection of luminescent porous silicon NPs into the right side tumor. Imaging was performed with an eXplore Optix system. Adapted with permission.^[68] Copyright 2013, Nature Publishing Group. b) Image intensity profiles obtained under continuous wave and time-gated conditions for mice subcutaneously injected with QDs emitting at 705 nm. A pulsed 630 nm LED array was used for optical excitation. The inset shows the images of one of the injected mice under both imaging conditions. Adapted with permission.^[69] Copyright 2009, SPIE. c) Schematic representation of the in vivo TGI system designed by Zheng et. al. TGI is enabled by the synchronization of an optical chopper with the pulsed 980 nm laser used as excitation source. Reproduced with permission.^[72] Copyright 2016, American Chemical Society. d) NIR (900-1700 nm) fluorescence images obtained for a C57/Bl mouse after oral administration of Nd³⁺-doped NPs (top row) and for a control mouse (bottom row). Excitation was achieved by a pulsed 808 nm laser and the images were collected under pseudo-continuous wave conditions (no delay time between the end of each laser pulse and image acquisition) and time-gated conditions (1 μs delay time). Adapted with permission.^[25] Copyright 2016, Wiley-VCH.

Based on these successful results, Jin's group developed a similar system for small animal TGI and tested its performance for in vivo imaging in mice subcutaneously injected with

Yb³⁺/Tb³⁺ co-doped UCNPs.^[72] The energy transfer from Yb³⁺ ions (excited at 980 nm) to Tb³⁺ ions (emitting at 800 nm) allows imaging in the first biological window using these NPs as contrast agents. Their TGI system relied on a pulsed 980 nm laser diode for excitation and an EMCCD camera for detection, as is schematically represented in **Figure 5c**. A high-speed mechanical chopper (5 kHz maximum frequency) placed between a camera lens and a microscope eyepiece was synchronized in antiphase to the excitation source using a homemade pulse synchronizer. These elements allowed generating a delay time of 25 μ s between the end of each laser pulse and the image acquisition window. This approach resulted in a 12-fold improvement in the image contrast with respect to that achieved under CW conditions (in this case, an 800 ± 6 nm bandpass filter was placed before the camera to minimize the background). The overall intensity was much lower in the TGI case, however, as the average counts in the NP injection area were reduced by almost a factor of 7.

Besides improving the contrast, the authors noted a marked reduction in the laser-induced heating in the TGI case when compared to CW imaging. In the latter case, a 30-second-long exposure to the excitation light resulted in a skin temperature increase of more than 25 degrees, whereas the pulsed excitation required for TGI enabled to keep this temperature increase below 5 degrees. The excitation wavelength (980 nm) used in this work, as we mentioned previously, overlaps with an absorption band of water and is therefore not optimal for bioimaging, as it will translate in undesired laser-induced heating. This was enhanced in this case by a high excitation power density ($3.18 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$), which translated in the remarkable temperature increment observed under CW conditions.

The reduced laser-induced heating achieved by pulsed excitation can be further minimized by choosing long-lifetime NPs that can be optically excited at a different wavelength.^[46a] Neodymium-doped NPs, which present an excitation band at around 800 nm,^[73] were employed by D. Jaque's group for in vivo TGI in 2016.^[25] As explained in section 3.1, NPs

doped with Nd^{3+} ions had already been explored as fluorescent contrast agents both in NIR-I and NIR-II, enabling autofluorescence-free imaging through emission wavelength selection.^[17a, 74] The experimental system used for TGI in this case relied on an 808 nm laser diode operating in pulsed mode for optical excitation, while detection was achieved using an InGaAs CCD camera (sensitive in the 900-1700 nm range) making this the first TGI system operating beyond the first biological window. For generating the delay between the excitation pulse and image acquisition, an electronic delay circuit was introduced between the pulsed laser source and the camera. This circuit allowed tuning the gating time between 1 and 200 μs . The in vivo performance of the system was evaluated in C57Bl/6 mice, whose black pigmentation causes an intense autofluorescence background in the NIR.^[36] The mice were orally or subcutaneously inoculated with Nd^{3+} -doped NaGdF_4 NPs with an average fluorescence lifetime of 90 μs . As shown in **Figure 5d**, 1 μs delay time was sufficient to eliminate the autofluorescence background that was present in the pseudo-CW images (obtained by removing the delay circuit from the system) in the mouse orally inoculated with NPs as well as in the control case. This delay time also allowed isolating the NP fluorescence from intrinsic organ autofluorescence in subsequent ex vivo biodistribution experiments. With respect to the system presented by Zheng et al., this TGI approach enabled shorter gating times, which helped detecting the NP signal and obtaining high contrast images at lower excitation power densities ($1 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$). This should help minimize the adverse thermal effects due to prolonged laser irradiation, although no surface temperature measurements were reported.

3.2.2. Persistent luminescence

In this section, we will describe the experimental basis and most relevant achievements obtained through persistent luminescence nanoparticles (hereafter PLNPs) for in vivo imaging.^[75] In this approach, the time gap separating the luminescence emission from the previous optical excitation of the material is quantitatively scaled up, as for “persistent” we

mean that luminescence lasts for at least several seconds and up to a few days after excitation. Different from other commonly used luminescent nanomaterials, PLNPs store their energy at defects or electron traps, and thereafter slowly release it through photon emission without requiring continuous excitation.^[76] Thus, although all the techniques described in this work are here generically grouped under the “fluorescence imaging” epigraph, we should accurately refer to PLNPs as phosphorescent materials.^[77]

From a methodological viewpoint, what clearly differentiates PLNPs-based *in vivo* imaging from TGI, analyzed in the previous section, it is that the former does not require neither pulsed excitation nor the introduction of a delay between excitation and collection, as the latter mandatorily does. Hence, the long-lasting phosphorescence nature of PLNPs allows for an experimental design where a complete spatiotemporal separation of optical excitation and imaging is feasible, and indeed frequently chosen. The implications for a background-free *in vivo* imaging are immediate, as the use of PLNPs directly implies that no excitation light or autofluorescence is anymore present by the time of collecting the signal.

As will be explained in the following lines, the PLNPs as *in vivo* contrast agents offer the very attractive possibility to actually disengage the collection of the signal from the precedent excitation, with absolutely no overlap of the two happening at the same time. Therefore, the research community working on PLNPs is optically charging the material in laboratory conditions and injecting it into the live specimen afterwards, where the signal collection takes place while the excitation source is off. As the autofluorescence is only present in the few nanoseconds after the excitation (or so to say, after the optical charge), even if the PLNPs are charged after being injected in the live specimen, image collection can be started well after the excitation light has been switched off. Then, the autofluorescence is no longer present, thus not creating any undesired background in the collected image. Interestingly, most of the recently published *in vivo* implementation of PLNPs explicitly highlight the

added possibility to sequentially recharge the PLNPs several times through orange/red or near-infrared optical excitation once the PLNPs have been injected in the live specimen under study. Although usually the afterglow time is noticeably lower than the one measured after excitation at shorter (UV/Vis) wavelengths, that possibility greatly increases the usefulness of the PLNPs as *in vivo* imaging contrast agents.

The first brick in our analysis of the latest PLNPs achievements goes through a brief illustrative selection of the variety of successfully developed materials. There have been a few different pioneering works on PNLPs to note in that material development area. Q. le Masne de Chermont et al. published an early report in 2007^[78] about Eu^{3+} , Dy^{3+} and Mn^{2+} tri-doped $\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{Zn}_{0.9}\text{Mg}_{0.9}\text{Si}_2\text{O}_6$ NPs. The broadband UV excitation, centered at 350 nm, produced persistent luminescence mostly in the near infrared spectral range, with the maximum located at 690 nm. The radiation was detectable for 24 hours when kept in the dark, but in terms of *in vivo* imaging the intensity of emission decays 2 orders of magnitude during the first 5 minutes immediately after excitation. The authors reported *in vivo* biodistribution imaging in mice for up to 30 min after NP administration. Remarkably, the lowest dose administered to mice produced a detectable signal-to-noise ratio above 5. In 2014, T. Maldiney et al. published a report on $\text{ZnGa}_{1.995}\text{Cr}_{0.005}\text{O}_4$ (referred as n-ZGO) PLNPs, with their emission centered at 695 nm.^[76c] The persistent luminescence emission decays 2 min after the end of the UV (290 nm) excitation. The insightful novelty is that the very same PLNPs also show the key feature of acquiring persistent emission up to 3 min after excitation through a spectrally different pathway, with orange/red light (550 nm), ended. Therefore, this second excitation pathway at longer wavelength offers the attractive feature of allowing repeated charge cycles after injecting the n-ZGO PLNPs to the specimen. For future developments of the material, though, the large acquisition times (> 1 min) featured for *in vivo* experiments must be taken into account.

Also interesting from the material development standpoint viewpoint is the work of B. Zheng et al., where light-tracked photothermal agents were developed as hybrid nanoparticles made by combining $\text{CaZnTiO}_3:0.1\% \text{Pr}^{3+}$ persistent luminescent phosphors, indocyanine green dye (photothermal delivery vector itself) and a mesoporous silica nanosphere as a template.^[79] To cover all different kind of PLNPs materials, the work by X. Zhen et al. using organic semiconductor NPs for subcutaneous imaging at 530 nm after UV excitation must be noted.^[80] The reported signal-to-noise ratio for the persistent luminescence (labeled in the manuscript as ultra-long phosphorescence) guided lymph node in vivo imaging is as high as 40, -acquisition time of 10s- while it is impossible to differentiate the lymph nodes from the normal tissue using fluorescence imaging of quantum dots emitting at approximately the same wavelength as the PLNPs.

It is beyond the scope of this work to carry out a comprehensive review of all the existing research in PNLPs. We will therefore discuss in the rest of this section some additional very recent works, and highlighting those among them better serving the purpose of analyzing the removal of autofluorescence from a methodological standpoint. Among the increasing wave of recent publications in this branch of research, it is worth noting the work of L. Song et al., where repeatable activation of $\text{SrAl}_2\text{O}_4:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ PLNPs by soft X-ray is reported, achieving high sensitivity long-term imaging.^[81] The quantitative highlight of this paper is how the 90-second-long X-ray in vivo irradiation (truly a recharge, as X-ray radiation was also used for the original PLNPs excitation prior to injection) accomplished a 30-fold enhance with respect to the intensity level to which the emission has decayed 1 h after intratumoral injection.

From a methodological point of view, the already mentioned work of T. Maldiney et al. comparatively discussed the merits of NIR-I QDs and (generically considered) PLNPs^[76c]. The former showed better absolute sensitivity and total emitted light, while the latter showed improved target-to-background ratio and relative sensitivity (**Figure 6**). The authors also

demonstrated the PLNPs enable real-time imaging of physiological phenomenon studied in vivo, such as tracking injected cells.

Playing with different excitation wavelengths and rendering different time scales for the afterglow, J. Lei et al. reported ultra-small $\text{Cr}^{3+}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ -doped ZnSn_2O_4 NPs emitting NIR persistent luminescence centered at 800 nm.^[82] Interestingly, that material allows profiting from the rich diversity of energy trap configurations, so that persistent luminescence is sequentially achieved following initial pre-injection charging at 254 nm, and subsequent in vivo excitation at 650 nm and 808 nm. A tradeoff between the wavelength used and the time length of the afterglow is clearly observed. Thus, the NIR luminescence persisted for more than 30 min once the UV irradiation ceased, but when recharging the nanoparticles with 650 nm and 808 nm excitation later in the same experiment, the NIR persistent luminescence lasted more than 10 min and at least 5 min, respectively. Moreover, the subsequent recharge of the $\text{Cr}^{3+}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ -doped ZnSn_2O_4 NPs carried out at those two larger excitation wavelengths (namely 650 nm and 808 nm) results in the signal-to-noise-ratio values returning to those reached after the initial optical charge with a 254 nm UV lamp. What makes this work especially insightful is that the provided set of data quantitatively shows the necessary trade-off that characterizes the persistent luminescence approach. That is, the direct proportionality between time passed after the charge (excitation) of the material for signal collection to happen, and the acquisition time; (i.e. the later the time point chosen for the measurement, the longer the acquisition time needs to be). In this work, reported acquisition times are 60 s, signal collection >5 min after LED irradiation, down to 5 s when mice images, were taken immediately after LED irradiation.

Figure 6. Persistent luminescence-based imaging. In vivo comparison of negatively charged QDs and PLNPs (ZGO), after intramuscular (a) and intravenous (b,c) injection in healthy mice. The experiments were conducted by injecting the same amount (50 μg per mouse) of QDs and PLNPs. The emission intensity is expressed in false color counts (1 count D 2,800 photons $\text{s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{sr}^{-1}$). The luminescence intensity, measured along the vertical line plotted in the images, is shown in each case. Reproduced with permission.^[76c] Copyright 2013, Nature Publishing Group.

In terms of multifunctionality, the $\text{mSiO}_2@\text{Gd}_3\text{Ga}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Cr}^{3+},\text{Nd}^{3+}$ ($\text{mSiO}_2@\text{GGO}$) PLNPS show persistent luminescence at 745 nm more than 3 h after UV excitation, but also feature fluorescence emission in the second biological window (1067 nm) under 808nm excitation – more suitable for deep tissue imaging^[83]. The presence of a high Gd^{3+} concentration on the crystalline host makes the system also suitable for T1 magnetic resonance imaging. During the experiments to ascertain the potential for in vivo imaging of this system, the persistent luminescence signal was recorded in the whole body within 5 min. An additional highlight demonstrating the useful removal of background autofluorescence is the work published in mid-2017 by J. Wang et al.^[84] applying zinc gallogermanate PLNPs ($\text{Zn}_{1+x}\text{Ga}_{2-2x}\text{Ge}_x\text{O}_4:\text{Cr}$, 0

$\leq x \leq 0.5$, ZGGO:Cr) for autofluorescence-free targeted tumor imaging. The signal of the persistent emission at around 700 nm from these PLNPs at the tumor site reached a maximum 1 hour after excitation, decreasing gradually after that. The advantages to avoid autofluorescence background during the signal collection appear clearly depicted in **Figure 7**, very advantageously comparing these PLNPs with other NIR contrast agents injected in mice at the same dose. Moreover, that aforementioned signal from the tumor site could still be visualized 5 h after the excitation.

Figure 7. Persistent luminescence-based imaging (II). (a) Schematic representation of the experimental procedure for autofluorescence-free imaging using ZGGO:Cr NPs ($x = 0.2$) as contrast agents. (b) In vivo NIR fluorescence images as obtained in mice intravenously injected with ZGGO:Cr ($x = 0.2$) nanoparticles, cyanine derivative dye, and Ag₂Se. The images were acquired 1 hour after contrast agent injection. The injected dosage of ZGGO:Cr, cyanine derivative dye, and Ag₂Se was kept at 1 μ g. Reproduced with permission.^[84] Copyright 2017, American Chemical Society.

Other recent works on PLNPs reported exciting applications about oral administration,^[85] carcinoma imaging and luminescence-guided surgery^[86] and therapeutic engineering tracking of mesenchymal stem cells.^[87] Further information can be found in a recent review authored by J. Wang et al.^[75]

In summary, PLNPs research is nowadays living an intense stage of development, as the field is maturing consistently with increasingly more *in vivo* studies successfully tested at very diverse showcases of *in vivo* fluorescence imaging.

4. Conclusion and outlook

As reviewed in the sections above, there are different approaches to suppress or at least reduce the autofluorescence background, an intrinsic issue greatly limiting the sensitivity and achievable resolution of fluorescence imaging. The division in two blocks that we have chosen for Section 3 displays a clear physical distinction of the mechanisms lying behind each of the described methodologies. Therefore, as a bottom line, we can differentiate signal from background noise based in *(a)* a spectral difference or *(b)* slicing the timeline after the excitation stopped. That chosen structure also allows the reader to chronologically track the evolution of the field. That is, historically starting with the selection of NIR excitation wavelengths -even at the microscopy level for *in vitro* - that were looking to minimize, if not eliminate, the background by switching away from UV excitation wavelengths. In addition, that trend continued when developing experimental methods for the more challenging *in vivo* fluorescence imaging. However, in such a biochemically complex framework as the biological milieu, with so many different autofluorescence sources disturbing the *in vivo* imaging procedure, it is almost impossible to work with an excitation wavelength that would not cause any kind of optical response from some of the chemical components present in tissues.

As the aim of this work has a mostly methodological emphasis, no comprehensive and quantitative overview of the QY value of the materials involved on each of the four approaches discussed in Section 3 has been carried out. The issue of a possible trade-off between autofluorescence reduction (and even suppression of it) and a corresponding reduction in the QY (and then, in the brightness) by choosing certain required materials must

be kept in mind. Anyways, at least for the wavelength-based methods, the research field of fluorescence in vivo imaging is definitively moving towards NIR-I excitation/NIR-II emission nanoprobe, pursuing not only minimizing autofluorescence, but also looking for higher penetration depth and better optical contrast. Water-dispersible quantum dots and lanthanide-doped NPs (among NIR-II emitting nanoprobe) are able to reach QY values in the 5-15% range or higher. Regarding the lifetime-based methods, TGI can in general be implemented with NIR-I and NIR-II materials featuring relatively long lifetimes ($> 100\text{ns}$) with already well-tested QY values, high enough for in vivo imaging. Finally, about the persistent NIR luminescent materials as relatively novel kind, there is yet a scarcity of rigorous studies about their QY.

The emission wavelength selection is nowadays widely applied, especially because that method pays off for in vivo fluorescence imaging far beyond the autofluorescence background reduction. That is, in terms of other additional top-notch benefits for in vivo imaging, it has already been clearly demonstrated that shifting to NIR-II brings deeper penetration and better optical contrast of the recorded signal (as longer NIR wavelengths suffer less absorption and scattering when propagating through tissues). Even without a careful design of the experimental setups for spectral filtering, the research groups looking into fluorescent contrast agents emitting beyond 1000 nm are somehow implementing de facto emission wavelength selection, thus translating into an effective reduction of the autofluorescence background.

On a deeper look to establish insightful differences between the four pathways discussed in this work, a brief analysis of the requirements needed to perform each of them in terms of materials properties vs. setup, engineering becomes necessary. All studied methodologies (both wavelength- and lifetime-based) require luminescent materials scoring well in terms of absorption coefficient and quantum yield. In the other hand, the relative importance of the

setup design is highly relevant for a methodology such as TGI, as a pulsed excitation and delay stage for the signal is mandatory. Among the studied procedurals, TGI is the methodology that demands both materials with relatively long fluorescence lifetimes (ideally, longer than a few μs) and accounting for the aforementioned specific components of the setup.

Although PLNPs belong to a more restricted class of materials than those used in TGI, -by featuring the less common asset of persistent luminescence (phosphorescence)-, their required setup is entirely free of the specific elements required for TGI, what greatly simplifies *in vivo* image acquisition. Moreover, the excitation (illumination) tool can be removed from the scene entirely by the time the image collection starts, which also works towards a simplification of the conditions surrounding the living specimen. Therefore, although the current landscape of available PLNPs materials is still limited, their use as looks like the more straightforward to get rid of the autofluorescence background.

What about the future? The excitation wavelength selection has already provided to this research field the improvement what it could, as the gamut of possible excitation wavelengths is narrowly determined by the absorption maxima of the fluorophores. Besides, as already explained, there are no completely autofluorescence-free excitation wavelengths, as the variety of absorbing autofluorophores is so wide. Regarding emission wavelength selection, for sure the research community will continue exploring the opportunities, via emission wavelength selection that materials emitting within the NIR-II spectral range have to offer, as that is a well-consolidated trend nowadays.

In the opinion of the authors of the present work, PLNPs constitute a quite radical and promising avenue to achieve autofluorescence-free *in vivo* images, but some shortcomings need an answer for a successful, widely extended implementation. PLNPs displaying longer afterglow time rechargeable through high-penetrating NIR-I excitation wavelengths and,

more importantly, featuring high brightness, are thus substantially needed. Yet, the long acquisition times (few seconds to tens of seconds) remain as the main conceptual drawback of persistent luminescence approach to fluorescence imaging. Although that issue hinders PLNPS implementation for real-time monitoring of (patho)physiological processes, those phosphorescent nanoprobe may likely play an outstanding role within the future clinical landscape, for instance on intraoperative imaging (imaging of tumors during surgery is important to ensure that the tumor be completely excised and thus prevent recurrence while avoiding unnecessary tissue removal that would contribute to morbidity and loss-of-function). Transition metals-doped nanoparticles, organic semiconductors and other material families will continuously swell the ranks of the available PLNPs systems and thus the research field, leaving behind the pure materials science developmental phase, will likely supply in the next years a carefully tailored new generation of PLNPs, much better suited for the requirements of in vivo fluorescence imaging.

TGI can be effectively extended towards new challenging proof-of-concepts and the acquisition of fluorescence images in specific pre-clinical contexts demanding a more radical suppression of the autofluorescence. Yet, the decrease in the absolute signal collected (by cutting out the first several hundred of nanoseconds of signal emission) certainly constitutes a drawback, although its impact can be foreseeably reduced in the next years through technological development, both at “delay electronics” and materials sides. An honest assessment of other TGI limitations accounts for making a bit more complex the required set ups than for other methodological approaches to fluorescence in vivo imaging. Still, TGI method grants the feasibility of taking full benefit of the more straightforward advantage of fluorescence imaging with respect of other imaging modalities (MRI, PET, CT), applied to real-time monitoring of different dynamical metabolic processes and patho-physiological perturbations.

In summary, all the intense research in autofluorescence removal cumulated during the last two decades constitute a rational guarantee for the bright future of in vivo fluorescence imaging, increasing the chances for continuing a smooth translation from lab bench to bedside.

Acknowledgements

A. Benayas thanks the European Commission as this project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No. 709270 "TEMPTATION".

Received: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Revised: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Published online: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

References

- [1] a) R. Weissleder, M. J. Pittet, *Nature* **2008**, *452*, 580-589; b) S. Andersson-Engels, C. af Klinteberg, K. Svanberg, S. Svanberg, *Phys. Med. Biol.* **1997**, *42*, 815; c) E. Betzig, G. H. Patterson, R. Sougrat, O. W. Lindwasser, S. Olenych, J. S. Bonifacino, M. W. Davidson, J. Lippincott-Schwartz, H. F. Hess, *Science* **2006**, *313*, 1642-1645; d) G. H. Patterson, J. Lippincott-Schwartz, *Science* **2002**, *297*, 1873-1877.
- [2] a) Y. T. Lim, S. Kim, A. Nakayama, N. E. Stott, M. G. Bawendi, J. V. Frangioni, *Mol. Imaging* **2003**, *2*, 50-64; b) A. Bashkatov, E. Genina, V. Kochubey, V. Tuchin, *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **2005**, *38*, 2543; c) S. L. Jacques, *Phys. Med. Biol.* **2013**, *58*, R37-R61.
- [3] a) R. Weissleder, *Nat. Biotechnol.* **2001**, *19*, 316-317; b) A. M. Smith, M. C. Mancini, S. Nie, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2009**, *4*, 710-711.
- [4] E. Hemmer, P. Acosta-Mora, J. Méndez-Ramos, S. Fischer, *Journal of Materials Chemistry B* **2017**.
- [5] a) P. Reineck, B. C. Gibson, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2017**, *5*, 26; b) V. J. Pansare, S. Hejazi, W. J. Faenza, R. K. Prud'homme, *Chem. Mater.* **2012**, *24*, 812-827; c) E. Cassette, M. Helle, L. Bezdetnaya, F. Marchal, B. Dubertret, T. Pons, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2013**, *65*, 719-731.
- [6] B. R. Smith, S. S. Gambhir, *Chem. Rev* **2017**, *117*, 901-986.
- [7] G. Hong, A. L. Antaris, H. Dai, *Nature Biomedical Engineering* **2017**, *1*, 0010.
- [8] a) O. T. Bruns, T. S. Bischof, D. K. Harris, D. Franke, Y. Shi, L. Riedemann, A. Bartelt, F. B. Jaworski, J. A. Carr, C. J. Rowlands, *Nature Biomedical Engineering* **2017**, *1*, 0056; b) G. S. Hong, Y. P. Zou, A. L. Antaris, S. Diao, D. Wu, K. Cheng, X. D. Zhang, C. X. Chen, B. Liu, Y. H. He, J. Z. Wu, J. Yuan, B. Zhang, Z. M. Tao, C. Fukunaga, H. J. Dai, *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, 9.
- [9] a) D.-E. Lee, H. Koo, I.-C. Sun, J. H. Ryu, K. Kim, I. C. Kwon, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2012**, *41*, 2656-2672; b) M. de Jong, J. Essers, W. M. van Weerden, *Nat. Rev. Cancer* **2014**, *14*, 481.
- [10] J. V. Frangioni, *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2003**, *7*, 626-634.

- [11] K. Koenig, H. Schneckenburger, *Journal of fluorescence* **1994**, *4*, 17-40.
- [12] R. Richards-Kortum, E. Sevick-Muraca, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.* **1996**, *47*, 555-606.
- [13] B. R. Masters, B. Chance, *Fluorescent and luminescent probes for biological activity* **1993**, 44-56.
- [14] M. Monici, G. Agati, P. Mazzinghi, F. Fusi, P. A. Bernabei, S. Landini, P. R. Ferrini, R. Pratesi, in *BiOS Europe'96*, International Society for Optics and Photonics, **1996**, pp. 180-187.
- [15] a) M. Fitzmaurice, J. O. Bordagaray, G. L. Engelmann, R. Richards-Kortum, T. Kolubayev, M. S. Feld, N. B. Ratliff, J. R. Kramer, *American heart journal* **1989**, *118*, 1028-1038; b) M. Sartori, R. Sauerbrey, S. Kubodera, F. Tittel, R. Roberts, P. Henry, *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* **1987**, *23*, 1794-1797.
- [16] a) X. Shao, W. Zheng, Z. Huang, *J. Biomed. Opt.* **2011**, *16*, 067005-067005-067008; b) S.-i. Yamagishi, K. Fukami, T. Matsui, *International journal of cardiology* **2015**, *185*, 263-268; c) G. J. Ughi, H. Wang, E. Gerbaud, J. A. Gardecki, A. M. Fard, E. Hamidi, P. Vacas-Jacques, M. Rosenberg, F. A. Jaffer, G. J. Tearney, *JACC: Cardiovascular Imaging* **2016**, *9*, 1304-1314.
- [17] a) I. Villa, A. Vedda, I. Cantarelli, M. Pedroni, F. Piccinelli, M. Bettinelli, A. Speghini, M. Quintanilla, F. Vetrone, U. Rocha, C. Jacinto, E. Carrasco, F. Rodríguez, Á. Juarranz, B. del Rosal, D. Ortgies, P. Gonzalez, J. Solé, D. García, *Nano Res.* **2015**, *8*, 649-665; b) C.-K. Park, H. Cho, *Journal of Nanomaterials* **2015**, *16*, 289; c) Y. Inoue, K. Izawa, S. Kiryu, A. Tojo, K. Ohtomo, *Mol. Imaging* **2008**, *7*, 7290.2008. 0003; d) Y. Inoue, K. Izawa, K. Yoshikawa, H. Yamada, A. Tojo, K. Ohtomo, *European Journal of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging* **2007**, *34*, 2048-2056; e) T. Troy, D. Jekic-McMullen, L. Sambucetti, B. Rice, *Mol. Imaging* **2004**, *3*, 9-23; f) S. Bhaumik, J. DePuy, J. Klimash, *Lab animal* **2007**, *36*, 40.
- [18] a) N. R. Baker, *Annu. Rev. Plant Biol.* **2008**, *59*, 89-113; b) K. Maxwell, G. N. Johnson, *J. Exp. Bot.* **2000**, *51*, 659-668; c) C. Buschmann, *Photosynth. Res.* **2007**, *92*, 261-271; d) G. Krause, E. Weis, *Annu. Rev. Plant Biol.* **1991**, *42*, 313-349.
- [19] S. L. Ustin, A. A. Gitelson, S. Jacquemoud, M. Schaepman, G. P. Asner, J. A. Gamon, P. Zarco-Tejada, *Remote Sensing of Environment* **2009**, *113*, S67-S77.
- [20] a) N. A. Welschmeyer, *Limnology and Oceanography* **1994**, *39*, 1985-1992; b) T. Gillbro, V. Sundström, Å. Sandström, M. Spangfort, B. Andersson, *FEBS Lett.* **1985**, *193*, 267-270.
- [21] G. H. Krause, E. Weis, *Photosynth. Res.* **1984**, *5*, 139-157.
- [22] a) G. Weagle, P. E. Paterson, J. Kennedy, R. Pottier, *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology* **1988**, *2*, 313-320; b) R. H. Pottier, Y. F. A. Chow, J. P. LaPlante, T. G. Truscott, J. C. Kennedy, L. A. Beiner, *Photochem. Photobiol.* **1986**, *44*, 679-687.
- [23] K. Konig, A. Kienle, W.-H. Boehncke, R. Kaufmann, A. Ruck, T. Meier, R. Steiner, *OPTICAL ENGINEERING-BELLINGHAM-INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY FOR OPTICAL ENGINEERING-* **1994**, *33*, 2945-2945.
- [24] H. Holmes, J. Kennedy, R. Pottier, F. Rossi, G. Weagle, *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology* **1995**, *29*, 199.
- [25] B. del Rosal, D. H. Ortgies, N. Fernández, F. Sanz-Rodríguez, D. Jaque, E. M. Rodríguez, *Adv. Mater.* **2016**, *28*, 10188-10193.
- [26] S. Ito, K. Wakamatsu, *The Pigmentary System: Physiology and Pathophysiology, Second Edition* **2007**, 282-310.
- [27] H. Zeng, C. MacAulay, B. Palcic, D. I. McLean, *Photochem. Photobiol.* **1995**, *61*, 639-645.

- [28] a) S. Kozikowski, L. Wolfram, R. Alfano, *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* **1984**, *20*, 1379-1382; b) J. M. Gallas, M. Eisner, *Photochem. Photobiol.* **1987**, *45*, 595-600; c) N. Kollias, G. Zonios, G. N. Stamatias, *Vib. Spectrosc.* **2002**, *28*, 17-23; d) M. Elleder, J. Borovanský, *The Histochemical Journal* **2001**, *33*, 273-281.
- [29] Z. Huang, H. Lui, X. Chen, A. Alajlan, D. I. McLean, H. Zeng, *J. Biomed. Opt.* **2004**, *9*, 1198-1205.
- [30] Z. Huang, H. Zeng, I. Hamzavi, A. Alajlan, E. Tan, D. I. McLean, H. Lui, *J. Biomed. Opt.* **2006**, *11*, 034010-034010-034016.
- [31] a) X. Han, H. Lui, D. I. McLean, H. Zeng, *J. Biomed. Opt.* **2009**, *14*, 024017-024017-024015; b) R. Eichhorn, G. Wessler, M. Scholz, D. Leupold, G. Stankovic, S. Buder, M. Stuecker, K. Hoffmann, *J. Biomed. Opt.* **2009**, *14*, 034033-034033-034037; c) M. A. Calin, S. V. Parasca, R. Savastru, M. R. Calin, S. Dontu, *Journal of cancer research and clinical oncology* **2013**, *139*, 1083-1104; d) S. Wang, J. Zhao, H. Lui, Q. He, H. Zeng, *Skin Research and Technology* **2013**, *19*, 20-26; e) I. A. Bratchenko, D. N. Artemyev, O. O. Myakinin, Y. A. Khristoforova, A. A. Moryatov, S. V. Kozlov, V. P. Zakharov, *J. Biomed. Opt.* **2017**, *22*, 027005-027005.
- [32] F. C. Piccolino, L. Borgia, E. Zinicola, M. Iester, S. Torrielli, *Ophthalmology* **1996**, *103*, 1837-1845.
- [33] A. Gabai, D. Veritti, P. Lanzetta, *Indian journal of ophthalmology* **2015**, *63*, 406.
- [34] C. N. Keilhauer, F. C. Delori, *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science* **2006**, *47*, 3556-3564.
- [35] A. V. Cideciyan, M. Swider, S. G. Jacobson, *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science* **2015**, *56*, 3393-3406.
- [36] B. del Rosal, I. Villa, D. Jaque, F. Sanz-Rodríguez, *Journal of Biophotonics* **2016**, *9*, 1059-1067.
- [37] S. Diao, G. Hong, A. L. Antaris, J. L. Blackburn, K. Cheng, Z. Cheng, H. Dai, *Nano Res.* **2015**, *8*, 3027-3034.
- [38] M. Viegas, T. Martins, F. Seco, A. Do Carmo, *European Journal of Histochemistry* **2009**, *51*, 59-66.
- [39] a) M. Y. Berezin, S. Achilefu, *Chemical reviews* **2010**, *110*, 2641-2684; b) A. Ehlers, I. Riemann, M. Stark, K. König, *Microscopy research and technique* **2007**, *70*, 154-161.
- [40] a) G. Chen, H. Qiu, P. N. Prasad, X. Chen, *Chemical Reviews* **2014**, *114*, 5161-5214; b) L. Y. Ang, M. E. Lim, L. C. Ong, Y. Zhang, *Nanomedicine* **2011**, *6*, 1273-1288; c) S. Hao, G. Chen, C. Yang, *Theranostics* **2013**, *3*, 331-345; d) M. Wang, G. Abbineni, A. Clevenger, C. Mao, S. Xu, *Nanomedicine: Nanotechnology, Biology and Medicine* **2011**, *7*, 710-729; e) F. Wang, D. Banerjee, Y. S. Liu, X. Y. Chen, X. G. Liu, *Analyst* **2010**, *135*, 1839-1854; f) F. Auzel, *Chemical reviews* **2004**, *104*, 139-174; g) L.-D. Sun, Y.-F. Wang, C.-H. Yan, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2014**, *47*, 1001-1009.
- [41] a) K. Park, Y. Kuo, V. Shvadchak, A. Ingargiola, X. Dai, L. Hsiung, W. Kim, H. Zhou, P. Zou, A. Levine, *bioRxiv* **2016**, 044057; b) X. Wu, G. Chen, J. Shen, Z. Li, Y. Zhang, G. Han, *Bioconjugate Chem.* **2015**, *26*, 166-175.
- [42] M. Nyk, R. Kumar, T. Y. Ohulchanskyy, E. J. Bergey, P. N. Prasad, *Nano Lett.* **2008**, *8*, 3834-3838.
- [43] a) C. Vinegoni, D. Razansky, S. A. Hilderbrand, F. Shao, V. Ntziachristos, R. Weissleder, *Opt. Lett.* **2009**, *34*, 2566-2568; b) Z. Tian, G. Chen, X. Li, H. Liang, Y. Li, Z. Zhang, Y. Tian, *Lasers in medical science* **2010**, *25*, 479-484.
- [44] L. Xiong, Z. Chen, Q. Tian, T. Cao, C. Xu, F. Li, *Anal. Chem.* **2009**, *81*, 8687-8694.
- [45] a) G. M. Hale, M. R. Querry, *Appl. Opt.* **1973**, *12*, 555-563; b) L. Kou, D. Labrie, P. Chylek, *Appl. Opt.* **1993**, *32*, 3531-3540.

- [46] a) L. M. Maestro, P. Haro-González, B. Del Rosal, J. Ramiro, A. Caamano, E. Carrasco, A. Juarranz, F. Sanz-Rodríguez, J. G. Solé, D. Jaque, *Nanoscale* **2013**, *5*, 7882-7889; b) P. Haro-González, W. T. Ramsay, L. M. Maestro, B. del Rosal, K. Santacruz-Gomez, M. del Carmen Iglesias-de la Cruz, F. Sanz-Rodríguez, J. Y. Chooi, P. R. Sevilla, M. Bettinelli, D. Choudhury, A. K. Kar, J. G. Solé, D. Jaque, L. Paterson, *Small* **2013**, *9*, 2162-2170.
- [47] Q. Zhan, J. Qian, H. Liang, G. Somesfalean, D. Wang, S. He, Z. Zhang, S. Andersson-Engels, *ACS Nano* **2011**, *5*, 3744-3757.
- [48] a) Y.-F. Wang, G.-Y. Liu, L.-D. Sun, J.-W. Xiao, J.-C. Zhou, C.-H. Yan, *ACS Nano* **2013**, *7*, 7200-7206; b) J. Shen, G. Chen, A.-M. Vu, W. Fan, O. S. Bilsel, C.-C. Chang, G. Han, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2013**, *1*, 644-650; c) X. Xie, N. Gao, R. Deng, Q. Sun, Q.-H. Xu, X. Liu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 12608-12611; d) H. Wen, H. Zhu, X. Chen, T. F. Hung, B. Wang, G. Zhu, S. F. Yu, F. Wang, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2013**, *52*, 13419-13423.
- [49] G. S. Hong, S. Diao, J. L. Chang, A. L. Antaris, C. X. Chen, B. Zhang, S. Zhao, D. N. Atochin, P. L. Huang, K. I. Andreasson, C. J. Kuo, H. J. Dai, *Nat. Photonics* **2014**, *8*, 723-730.
- [50] K. Welsher, Z. Liu, S. P. Sherlock, J. T. Robinson, Z. Chen, D. Daranciang, H. Dai, *Nat Nano* **2009**, *4*, 773-780.
- [51] a) K. Welsher, S. P. Sherlock, H. Dai, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **2011**, *108*, 8943-8948; b) G. Hong, J. C. Lee, J. T. Robinson, U. Raaz, L. Xie, N. F. Huang, J. P. Cooke, H. Dai, *Nat Med* **2012**, *18*, 1841-1846.
- [52] a) G. Chen, F. Tian, Y. Zhang, Y. Zhang, C. Li, Q. Wang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2014**, *24*, 2481-2488; b) G. Hong, J. T. Robinson, Y. Zhang, S. Diao, A. L. Antaris, Q. Wang, H. Dai, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2012**, *51*, 9818-9821; c) P. Jiang, C. N. Zhu, Z. L. Zhang, Z. Q. Tian, D. W. Pang, *Biomaterials* **2012**, *33*, 5130-5135; d) Y. Zhang, G. Hong, Y. Zhang, G. Chen, F. Li, H. Dai, Q. Wang, *ACS Nano* **2012**, *6*, 3695-3702; e) C. Li, Y. Zhang, M. Wang, Y. Zhang, G. Chen, L. Li, D. Wu, Q. Wang, *Biomaterials* **2014**, *35*, 393-400.
- [53] Z. Tao, G. Hong, C. Shinji, C. Chen, S. Diao, A. L. Antaris, B. Zhang, Y. Zou, H. Dai, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2013**, *52*, 13002-13006.
- [54] a) A. Benayas, F. Ren, E. Carrasco, V. Marzal, B. del Rosal, B. A. Gonfa, Á. Juarranz, F. Sanz-Rodríguez, D. Jaque, J. García-Solé, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2015**, *25*, 6650-6659; b) F. Ren, B. del Rosal, S. Y. An, F. Yang, E. Carrasco, A. Benayas, J. K. Oh, D. Jaque, Á. J. de la Fuente, F. Vetrone, *Particle & Particle Systems Characterization* **2017**, *34*; c) Y. Imamura, S. Yamada, S. Tsuboi, Y. Nakane, Y. Tsukasaki, A. Komatsuzaki, T. Jin, *Molecules* **2016**, *21*, 1080.
- [55] Z. Tao, X. Dang, X. Huang, M. D. Muzumdar, E. S. Xu, N. M. Bardhan, H. Song, R. Qi, Y. Yu, T. Li, W. Wei, J. Wyckoff, M. J. Birrer, A. M. Belcher, P. P. Ghoroghchian, *Biomaterials* **2017**, *134*, 202-215.
- [56] E. Soini, I. Hemmilä, *Clinical Chemistry* **1979**, *25*, 353-361.
- [57] E. Soini, H. Kojola, *Clinical Chemistry* **1983**, *29*, 65-68.
- [58] R. E. Connally, J. A. Piper, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* **2008**, *1130*, 106-116.
- [59] a) A. Vaasa, K. Ligi, S. Mohandessi, E. Enkvist, A. Uri, L. W. Miller, *Chem. Commun.* **2012**, *48*, 8595-8597; b) M. Rajendran, Lawrence W. Miller, *Biophys. J.* **2015**, *109*, 240-248; c) Y. Kodama, *PLoS One* **2016**, *11*, e0152484; d) C.-C. Tu, K. Awasthi, K.-P. Chen, C.-H. Lin, M. Hamada, N. Ohta, Y.-K. Li, *ACS Photonics* **2017**; e) H. Ma, B. Song, Y. Wang, D. Cong, Y. Jiang, J. Yuan, *Chemical Science* **2017**, *8*, 150-159; f) H. Ma, B. Song, Y. Wang, C. Liu, X. Wang, J. Yuan, *Dyes Pigm.* **2017**, *140*, 407-416.

- [60] a) R. Cubeddu, P. Taroni, G. Valentini, G. Canti, *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology* **1992**, *12*, 109-113; b) R. Cubeddu, P. Taroni, G. Valentini, *Vol. 32, SPIE*, **1993**, p. 6.
- [61] R. Cubeddu, G. Canti, P. Taroni, G. Valentini, *Lasers in Medical Science* **1997**, *12*, 200-208.
- [62] P. Gallant, A. Belenkov, G. Ma, F. Lesage, Y. Wang, D. Hall, L. McIntosh, in *Biomedical Topical Meeting*, Optical Society of America, Miami Beach, Florida, **2004**, p. WD2.
- [63] a) D. J. Hall, G. Ma, F. Lesage, P. Gallant (Art Advanced Research Technologies Inc), *WO2005043138 A1*, **2005**; b) W. F. Long, Y. Berube-Lauziere, L. Mcintosh *CA2505677 C*, **2004**; c) W. F. Long, Y. Berube-Lauziere, D. J. Hall, L. Mcintosh (Art Advanced Research Technologies Inc.), *US6992762 B2*, **2011**
- [64] S. Keren, O. Gheysens, C. S. Levin, S. S. Gambhir, *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* **2008**, *27*, 58-63.
- [65] G. Ma, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2013**, *5*, 2835-2844.
- [66] D. J. Hall, S.-H. Han, A. M. Chepetan, E. G. Inui, M. Rogers, L. L. Dugan, *Journal of Cerebral Blood Flow & Metabolism* **2012**, *32*, 23-32.
- [67] D. J. Hall, U. Sunar, S. Farshchi-Heydari, S.-H. Han, *Appl. Opt.* **2009**, *48*, D74-D78.
- [68] L. Gu, D. J. Hall, Z. Qin, E. Anglin, J. Joo, D. J. Mooney, S. B. Howell, M. J. Sailor, *Nat. Commun.* **2013**, *4*, 2326.
- [69] A. May, S. Bhaumik, S. S. Gambhir, C. Zhan, S. Yazdanfar, *J. Biomed. Opt.* **2009**, *14*, 060504-060504-060503.
- [70] J. W. Stouwdam, G. A. Hebbink, J. Huskens, F. C. J. M. van Veggel, *Chem. Mater.* **2003**, *15*, 4604-4616.
- [71] a) R. C. Leif, S. Yang, in *Progress in Biomedical Optics and Imaging - Proceedings of SPIE, Vol. 7568*, **2010**; b) Y. Lu, D. Jin, R. C. Leif, W. Deng, J. A. Piper, J. Yuan, Y. Duan, Y. Huo, *Cytometry Part A* **2011**, *79A*, 349-355; c) D. Jin, J. A. Piper, *Anal. Chem.* **2011**, *83*, 2294-2300; d) D. Jin, Y. Lu, R. C. Leif, S. Yang, M. Rajendran, L. W. Miller, *Current Protocols in Cytometry* **2014**; e) R. C. Leif, S. Yang, Y. Lu, D. Jin, S. Chambers, in *Progress in Biomedical Optics and Imaging - Proceedings of SPIE, Vol. 8225*, **2012**.
- [72] X. Zheng, X. Zhu, Y. Lu, J. Zhao, W. Feng, G. Jia, F. Wang, F. Li, D. Jin, *Anal. Chem.* **2016**, *88*, 3449-3454.
- [73] B. del Rosal, A. Pérez-Delgado, M. Misiak, A. Bednarkiewicz, A. S. Vanetsev, Y. Orlovskii, D. J. Jovanović, M. D. Dramićanin, U. Rocha, K. U. Kumar, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2015**, *118*, 143104.
- [74] G. Chen, T. Y. Ohulchanskyy, S. Liu, W.-C. Law, F. Wu, M. T. Swihart, H. Ågren, P. N. Prasad, *ACS Nano* **2012**, *6*, 2969-2977.
- [75] J. Wang, Q. Ma, Y. Wang, H. Shen, Q. Yuan, *Nanoscale* **2017**, *9*, 6204-6218.
- [76] a) Y. Li, M. Gecevicius, J. Qiu, *Chemical Society Reviews* **2016**, *45*, 2090-2136; b) T. Maldiney, C. Richard, J. Seguin, N. Wattier, M. Bessodes, D. Scherman, *ACS Nano* **2011**, *5*, 854-862; c) T. Maldiney, A. Bessière, J. Seguin, E. Teston, S. K. Sharma, B. Viana, A. J. J. Bos, P. Dorenbos, M. Bessodes, D. Gourier, D. Scherman, C. Richard, *Nature Materials* **2014**, *13*, 418.
- [77] H. W. Leverenz, *Science* **1949**, *109*, 183-195.
- [78] Q. le Masne de Chermont, C. Chanéac, J. Seguin, F. Pellé, S. Maîtrejean, J.-P. Jolivet, D. Gourier, M. Bessodes, D. Scherman, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **2007**, *104*, 9266-9271.
- [79] B. Zheng, H. B. Chen, P. Q. Zhao, H. Z. Pan, X L. Wu, X. Q. Gong, H. J. Wang, J. Chang, *ACS applied materials & interfaces* **2016**, *8*, 21603-21611.

- [80] X. Zhen, Y. Tao, Z. An, P. Chen, C. Xu, R. Chen, W. Huang, K. Pu, *Advanced Materials* **2017**, 29.
- [81] L. Song, X. H. Lin, X. R. Song, S. Chen, X. F. Chen, J. Li, H. H. Yang, *Nanoscale* **2017**, 9, 2718-2722.
- [82] J. L. Li, J. P. Shi, C. C. Wang, P. H. Li, Z. F. Yu, H. W. Zhang, *Nanoscale* **2017**, 9, 8631-8638.
- [83] J. Shi, X. Sun, S. Zheng, J. Li, X. Fu, H. Zhang, *Biomaterials* **2018**, 152, 15-23.
- [84] J. Wang, Q. Ma, X.-X. Hu, H. Liu, W. Zheng, X. Chen, Q. Yuan, W. Tan, *ACS Nano* **2017**, 11, 8010-8017.
- [85] Y. J. Li, X. P. Yan, *Nanoscale* **2016**, 8, 14965-14970.
- [86] T. Ai, W. Shang, H. Yan, C. Zeng, K. Wang, Y. Gao, T. Guan, C. Fang, J. Tian, *Biomaterials* **2018**.
- [87] S. Q. Wu, C. X. Yang, X. P. Yan, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2017**, 27.
- [88] B. del Rosal Rabes, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid **2017**.

Blanca del Rosal studied Physics at Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (Spain) and received her PhD in Photonics from the same institution in 2017. Her doctoral research was supervised by Prof. Daniel Jaque and focused on the in vivo applications of infrared-emitting nanoparticles for imaging, temperature sensing and photothermal therapy. In July 2017, she joined Prof. Baohua Jia's group at Swinburne University of Technology (Australia). Her current research is focused on the application of two-dimensional materials for biomedical applications.

Antonio Benayas received his PhD in Physics of Light & Matter (2012) from Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (Spain), presenting a thesis on spectroscopy-based multipurpose probes using confocal microscopy. Up to late 2016, supported by health-related funding agencies, he worked under Prof. F. Vetrone at Institut National de la Recherche Scientifique (Canada) developing near-infrared emitting nanoplatforms for in vivo imaging and thermometry. Currently he carries out an international project between the Stanford School of Medicine (USA) and the Materials Institute of Aveiro (Portugal), funded by the European Commission. His work focuses on bimodal nanoparticles for upgraded luminescence and photoacoustic imaging/sensing.

Tissue autofluorescence is the major contributor to background noise in in vivo NIR images, so that it complicates the detection of any NIR fluorescent marker used as contrast agents. A critical review of the numerous experimental approaches devised to perform in vivo autofluorescence-free images, together with a discussion on the main autofluorescence sources in the NIR, is presented here.

Autofluorescence

B. del Rosal* and A. Benayas*

Strategies to overcome autofluorescence in nanoprobe-driven in vivo fluorescence imaging

